

Title: The Impact of Clique Activities on The Socio-Economic Wellbeing of Residents in Bo City

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of clique activities on the socioeconomic well-being of residents in Bo City, highlighting the significant atrocities committed by the cliques and making recommendations based on its findings.

This research used a combination of quantitative and qualitative research designs. The study targeted 130 respondents. Key among those targeted were youths, police personnel, parents, clique group leaders, ghetto owners, the Family Support Unit of the Sierra Leone Police, staff of the Ministry of Social Welfare, and traders.

For this study, primary and secondary data sources were explored, and the data was analyzed using simple statistical techniques such as frequency counts, percentages, and measures of central tendency. The finding revealed that security personnel should continue to train and sensitize key actors and community members to detect and address early crime signals.

Findings from the study also revealed that a vast majority, 91%, of the targeted population believe cliques contribute little or nothing to the development of their communities.

Furthermore, it was revealed that clique activities in the community lead to social exclusion. Youths whose actions have been labelled as delinquent are often considered unfit for purpose and, therefore, excluded from community functions. Such exclusions reduce young people's ability to develop self-confidence.

The study concluded that the government should provide scholarships for school-going youths and effective free education so that people experiencing poverty can send their children to school. This will ultimately decrease clique activities and increase the socioeconomic well-being of residents in Bo.

Keywords: Clique, activities, socioeconomic, well-being, Bo

Introduction

Since the end of the 11 years of civil war in Sierra Leone, there has been a remarkable increase in the number of clique activities in the country. Their presence in most big cities in the country has been a serious concern for all stakeholders. Sporadic violent activities among teenagers in school-related activities have been a common occurrence in most parts of the country. This development has, over the past few years, been considered a security concern and, hence, a significant threat to the socioeconomic development of Sierra Leone. However, much insight into this recent development of clique groups and their activities has not received many empirical studies that can guide policymakers and other stakeholders in the dealings of clique-related activities in big towns, especially concerning the stability of those towns.

Thus, against this backdrop, this study aims to investigate cliques and their impact on the socioeconomic well-being of residents in Bo City. Although a study of cliques is often done during early childhood and adolescence, it is essential to note that they exist in all age groups. People who are part of a particular clique are bonded together by similar social characteristics such as race, ethnicity, economic status, physical outlook, etc. (Shalen Bishop, June 2011, Pepperdine University America)

In Sierra Leone, cliques are typically found among school-going adolescents, although they are often mixed with school dropouts. Since adolescents usually imitate similar cultural values, they are likely to become friends, and these friends are more likely to encourage aspects of their behavioural patterns, such as dress code, slang, and sometimes a particular way of walking.

According to Sociologists Patricia and Peter Adler¹ Middle School cliques often fall under four specific categories

- **The Popular Clique:** Members of a clique are generally known to have many friends in their school and have the most fun.
- **The Fringe Group:** members of this clique imitate the popular cliques' actions, structure and instructions but are not part of it. They are next to the popular kids.
- **The Friendship Circles:** Members share common beliefs, interests, and lifestyles; they seek to maintain their culture separate from the other cliques.
- **The Loners:** members of this group have very few friends and prefer to work alone. Some may be envious of those who belong to a different clique. (Adolescent cliques, Wikipedia the free Encyclopedia)

In Sierra Leone, many believe clique activities became more rampant during and after the 11-year civil war. It was after the war that youth violence began to gain momentum in the country. During the war, youths were the primary target for conscription by all the warring forces (soldiers, Rebels, civil militias, etc.). These youths were recruited, given arms and drugs, and they inflicted severe atrocities on innocent civilians. After the war, these youth were reunified in communities, and some were placed in educational institutions, schools, and other vocational training centres. These youths, who were commanders living at the expense of others, started to form groups where they could maintain superiority over others; as the formation of youth groups increased, competitions began to exist between and within different youth groups. This has resulted in violent behaviours among the youth in the country.

In Bo City, intermittent clique activities began, which were noticed in the early 1990s when school leagues were organized between secondary schools. One such event was in 1993 when the Christ The King College students clashed with the St. Andrew's Secondary School pupils, and a student was stabbed, and severe damages were done to the St Andrew's Secondary School building on 04 March 1993, at about 4 pm. Youth violence associated with clique activities has become more rampant in the city of Bo in recent years. On 09 November 2015, police in Bo arrested thirty-two (32) rival gang members from the Young Killer Kill Killer (YKKK) and Killer Kill Killer (KKK) clique members after they (the police) raided the township early morning that day. Concord Times Newspaper (14 March 2016) reported that residents in Bo had returned to the old days of going home early and closing business before dusk as some youth who belong to cliques terrorize residents. Even inside their houses, some residents in Bo are fearful at night as members of clique groups reportedly attack, rape women and girls, and cart away with whatever they can lay their hands on. Business houses, including petty traders, close their businesses earlier for fear of being attacked by these clique members who often carry with them dangerous weapons at night.

Additionally, on 10 November 2015, Awoko Newspaper also reported similar incidences of boys and girls belonging to clique groups in Bo going on a rampage and terrorizing residents. The paper further states that at gunpoint, these clique groups stole mobile phones, bags, money, and other valuables from people, especially those coming from nightclubs, bars, and restaurants at night. Those who show resistance in giving up their items stand the risk of being chopped by a machete, knives, and other dangerous items. Criminal exploits in this city have become more aggressive, operating in numbers and using weapons. They also target expatriates due to their perceived wealth (Munu. I, 2023). It is the total of these atrocities that gave Bo City the accolade of a hotspot of political violence. A proper understanding of these activities, especially as they relate to cliques, is the thrust of this paper.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptualization of Cliques: According to Trevor Romain (1998), a clique is a small group of individuals closely knit together and commonly share things. Early adolescence is the prime time for children to form social cliques. In the social sciences, a clique is a group of people interacting with each other and sharing similar interests. Belonging to a social group is part of the standard of social development regardless of Gender, ethnicity, or popularity. Cliques exist in all age groups, although they are most generally studied

during adolescence and middle childhood. Members of a particular clique are bonded through similar social features such as physical outlook, race, ethnicity, economic status, etc.

According to Exhibition 2014, Ainsley, Katie, Gabi, and Annada define a clique as a group of two or more people who exclude others and intensify loyalty to their beliefs, behaviours, values, and interests.

The social hierarchy places the famous students at the top and the solitary ones at the bottom. Popularity is something many boys and girls make strenuous efforts to achieve during their adolescence (Adler & Adler, 1995, 1998; Burstein)

Identification of different clique groups: Looking at the different definitions of a clique, we can see the differences between the many cliques to which people, especially youths, belong.

During the teenage years, students may join a particular clique to free themselves from the secondary school process's pain, worry, and agitation.

These cliques and the experiences behind them may influence young people's lived experiences. There are different types of cliques:

- Popular Cliques- People with a genuine desire and interest who encourage individuality and those who wish for popularity are controlled by a particular leader and believe they are superior to others. This superiority is demonstrated in sports, mayhem, academic excellence, dress code, entertainment, and more.
- Friendship Circles—Members of friendship circles seem to be groups of friends who share common values such as beliefs, interests, style, appearance, or hobbies.
- The Loners—Members of this group tend to have very few friends and prefer to work and be alone. Some may be jealous of those who belong to a different clique.

Reasons for the formation of clique groups: According to the Dissertation titled Youth Gang Membership by Daniel Stefan Hounslea, a child's social development is deeply rooted in opportunities; skills and recognition accrue during early interaction with family members, peers and teachers. Those youths who passed smoothly from secondary school to higher education had the lowest means of clique behaviour, and those with problems during subsequent schooling were more involved in clique activities.

Recent research conducted by Levitt and Venkatesh (2009) has suggested that illegal means, such as selling drugs, have become some clique member's source of steady employment.

As boys and girls go through the transitional period of life, they may acquire some new friends and lose formal friends. Friends and cliques develop, and their socioeconomic status and influence become known by all in the school. Some cliques are revered, whilst others are disliked. Because of admirable attributes like kindness, respectfulness, and smartness, certain cliques may attract more attention and be influenced and favoured by other students and educators (Bishop S, 2011).

Those whose families are maimed by death, illness, separation and transience and those who feel unloved as a result are those who are likely to commit crimes in order to gain social capital (Miller, 1998, p. 430).

Low-income families disrupted families, and low parental supervision is risk factors leading to clique membership.

Thornberry (2003) suggests that Adolescents whose parents have not graduated from high school are more prone to becoming gang members. Young people born into families where crime and gangs are familiar places help to demonstrate how subcultures are a way of life. Gaining a sense of identity contributes to young people joining cliques. Learnt behaviours from families contribute to young people engaging in clique activities. Parents and relatives may pass their values on to young people and introduce them to cliques.

Impact of clique groups: Forming groups of like individuals can benefit said individuals immensely. Building bonds with people can help develop social skills like collaboration and conflict resolution. Also, a group of genuine friends with similar interests can positively influence one's behaviour. They can help people try new things, boost their self-confidence, and help them develop their identity. In addition, a sound effect of social groups is that they fulfil that need to belong without negatively impinging upon one's decisions.

Developing social groups and cliques, while sometimes beneficial, can have many consequences. The lack of socialization between social groups makes people less prepared to make friends during adulthood. Cliques also put labels and stereotypes on groups of people, forcing people's true identities to remain hidden. In addition, the attributes that kids are rejected for are often the ones most respected outside of school and into adulthood. Forming an identity will be easy if these attributes are smothered by conformity.

In sociology, cliques are a plurality of individuals who share mechanical solidarities that permit them to care for one another and in the process, they form strong social networks. Those within the group, often known as in-group members, communicate and associate with each other more than those outside the group, often dubbed out-group members [Trevor Romain, 1998]. The formation of clique groups can be observed within different social environments throughout people's lives. Individuals can be part of multiple cliques, each forming and functioning independently. Despite some challenges, cliques are often considered necessary in some societies due to the peer pressure from interactions with individuals with standard features. The results associated with clique formations may be limitless, with varying degrees of impact. For example, a formal clique, such as a professional organization, would have a different influence than a social clique of close friends.

Generally, cliques perform the following functions for their membership:

Social isolation: The degree of separateness of an entity, with subjective interpretations, is commonly known as social isolation. This phenomenon can occur when cliques set themselves apart from other groups.

A clique can also involve a high social commitment to a specific group. A more substantial level of commitment results in an individual having less interaction with other social groups. Cliquish behaviour often involves repetition regarding activities, slang, choices, and manners, resulting in conflict with other cliques and creating instability for "outsiders." (Paolo Parigi, 2009). Individuals can also experience social isolation within their cliques if their values and behaviour differ from the rest of the group.

Members: Different factors affect how cliques are established and who is included in their membership. In some instances, people are subconsciously placed in a clique by association. For example, joining a basketball team can cause others to perceive one as an "athlete automatically". Many people may subconsciously gravitate toward a clique through their association with others. The sharing of common interests is the most peculiar way cliques are formed. As individuals interact with each other doing the simple things they enjoy, they often draw towards others who share the same passion. Being surrounded by persons with similar interests usually causes one to gain confidence and may make an individual feel more socially accepted.

Racial and ethnic inclinations usually vary according to the setting or time frame. In today's society, race is still prevalent, so race-related cliques have been formed. One memorable example of such a clique could be the Ku Klux Klan, a notorious white supremacy group.

Clique members often create distinct dress codes and communicate uniquely with each other. This makes a clique unique and gives each member a reassuring feeling that they belong to that specific group. As these cliques come together, it takes work to distinguish one from the other.

Social events like parties, significant dates, or private meetings can be organized based on the interactions of clique members. Clique members have a solid commitment to their respective groups. This shows the firmness of cliques and how people ultimately conform to these specific groups.

Conformity to peer groups determines achieving independence and autonomy as an adult. As young persons strive to become independent from their guardians or parents, they utilize the security and warmth given by the peer group and the associated self-confidence that comes with it to take the final step towards independence. This indicates that peer pressure is a compelling force in getting adolescents to put up certain behaviours. Such conformity enables the formation of friendship ties and full integration into peer groups (Laursen et al., 2021)

Additionally, the concept of homophile comes in handy here, especially as it relates to the formation of cliques. Homophile is a term used to describe the way people tend to connect with others because they share similar characteristics. The existence of homophiles is also very prevalent in today's society. This concept is a possible leading cause of clique formation.

On the subject of homophiles, people come together and link up for many different reasons. The most typical reason is that people who are close in a location can quickly bond with each other. Also, people who meet through family, workplace, and any activities that place people in contact with others often form personal relationships.

In some cases, the impact of homophiles can be seen when people in cliques get married. Furthermore, homophile has plenty to do with how social networks thrive.

Network Formation: Networking involves meeting new people to form relationships and work together for better opportunities. Some people find associating with a clique is a way to achieve what they cannot do alone. For example, some university students join a sorority or fraternity to gain a better advantage at getting a job

because someone may hire them who may be affiliated. Cliques go hand-in-hand with how people network and are common for those looking for jobs. [Frey and Fisher 2008]

Organization: Every clique has some form of organization that makes up the social interaction network (Frey & Fisher, 2008). Informal clique networks are groups that need a legitimate organizational structure that can be established and dissolved quickly. A clique known to be informal may consist of a person's friend group or co-workers and may also identify other more informal groups, such as criminal gangs (Fred Clow, 2008, as cited by S. Bishop, 2011)). On the other hand, a formal clique is one with a socially accepted organization that is hierarchical. A formal clique comprises members with a hierarchy of ranks with roles and responsibilities. Such cliques are found in professional organizations, businesses, and even family structures (Tichy, 1973). Culture is a very influential element in forming clique structures because boundaries established through variations in cultural aspects are continuous despite the variation in membership between times. For example, the differences in cultural aspects like language, beliefs, traditions, values, and more have always resulted in a distinct separation or boundary between groups of people, even though the members of that particular group are constantly changing. Complex relationships between languages and linguistic groups define multilingual societies (Manish Singh, 2023).

Improved interaction: The formation and disintegration of clique structures and patterns are not limited to adolescence. However, the level and number of interactions with clique groups are reduced, and the group type may vary. As people become adults, their social interpretations alter, and the formation of their cliques originates from their immediate environment rather than from common social characteristics. There should not be a mix-up between what a clique is and that of a crowd. It is because of the smaller size and specific boundaries of a group that cause the group formation to be referred to as a clique. In several ways and by the influence of the environment, a clique can develop with individuals interacting differently. The strong bond between clique members is due to the constant face-to-face interaction between the members. This interaction can create or dissolve the group, depending upon the level and quality of interaction. If face-to-face interaction is established regularly, then cohesion between individuals will develop. However, if the face-to-face interaction depreciates, the cohesive social bond between individuals will lose its strength (Witvliet & Van Lier, 2007)

Blocking External Social Influence: Cliques can block social influence from outside by influencing group members' emotions, opinions or behaviours (Cuijpers & Koot, 2011). In several ways, the perception of information between clique members can determine their behaviour pattern to a greater level than how they would have behaved if they had received the same information from another source. For instance, obtaining information from a family member is decoded and influences behaviour differently than receiving the same information from someone outside the clique structure. The satisfaction, interaction, and closeness between the clique groups where we involve ourselves develops and changes throughout the years. However, the individual and the group morph as time passes (Cuijpers & Koot, 2011).

Methodology

This study was conducted in Bo City, the second-largest city in Sierra Leone after Freetown. With a population of 756,975 (Male, 366,346 and female, 390,629), the city is the leading financial, educational, commercial, transportation, and urban centre after Freetown (Statistic-SL., 2021).

The end of the civil strife in Sierra Leone ushered in an increase in homicide, rape, armed robbery, and home invasion in Bo Town. Petty crime and pickpocketing of wallets, cell phones, and passports are widespread in the city. Over the past year, criminal exploits have become more aggressive, increasingly operating in numbers and using weapons, stated Sgt Joseph Momoh of The Family Support Unit at the Bo East Police Division.

This research used a combination of quantitative and qualitative research designs. The study targeted 130 respondents. Key among those targeted were youths, police personnel, parents, clique group leaders, ghetto owners, the Family Support Unit of the Sierra Leone Police, staff of the Ministry of Social Welfare, and traders.

Two data sources were explored for this study: primary study: primary and secondary sources. The ensuing data was analyzed using simple statistical techniques such as frequency counts, percentages, and measures of central tendency. The ensuing results are presented in charts and tables.

Data Presentation and Discussions

Characteristics of existing Clique groups in the study area: There is great awareness of the existence of clique activities within the city of Bo. Most renowned among these are The "Killer Kill Killer" (KKK), "Young Killer Kill Killer" (YKKK), "Money Over Blood" (MOB), "Skulls and Bones", and "State Of Stunners" (SOS). Of these groups, 75% are male teens, with only 25% making up for female counterparts.

Furthermore, the study reveals that the clique activities in the study area are colour-coded; that is, each clique group is known to use specific colours as their signature in everything they do. On this note, KKK is known to use Black, YKKK uses Red, MOB uses White, and SOS uses Blue.

Most of these clique groups undergo some form of an initiation process, which, in addition to the alcohol consumption, smoking of illegal substances, and tattooing their bodies, keep them together. Notable among the activities known for clique groups is their interest in stealing, Raping, fighting, and stabbing (See Figure 1) out-group members each time the opportunity avails itself. Interestingly, these groups also have leadership structures, and the group leaders punish members who break their codes of conduct.

Figure 1: Major atrocities committed by clique groups. Source: Primary Data, 2024

Impact of Clique Activities on the Well-being of Residents: The study Findings show that a vast majority, 91%, of the targeted population believe that cliques contribute little or nothing to the development of their communities. However, others believe that cliques sometimes contribute to community work within their communities, such as cleaning exercises and entertainment programs. However, some often end in chaos—such chaos results from the poor relationships among these groups. The rivalry between them is heightened during sports or entertainment competitions. Furthermore, it was revealed that clique activities in the community lead to social exclusion; that is, youths whose actions have been labelled as being delinquent are often considered not fit for purpose and, therefore, excluded from community functions. Such exclusions rub off young people's ability to develop self-confidence. Considering that these youngsters are supposed to be the future leaders of these communities, it becomes plausible to imagine that the future of such a community is bleak. Therefore, despite the mayhem caused by these clique youths, the actual and more lasting impact is the loss of quality human resources to handle the community's affairs. This will, in turn, lead to a low pace of development and a vicious cycle of recklessness for most of the inhabitants of that community.

Summary

Clique activities in the study area have impacted socioeconomic well-being immensely in diverse ways. Several people know the incidences and formation of cliques in the study area, and their acronyms are ubiquitous among young people in the community. Most popular among them are the KKK, YKKK, and MOB. These cliques are commonly identified by their dress code, portraying different colour codes.

Additionally, fighting, stabbing, stealing, and raping are the most common challenges posed by these groups. Despite the threats they pose to the peace and stability of the city based on the havoc they wreck, there is a more lasting impact. The loss of quality human resources to handle the community's affairs is a serious concern. This will, in turn, lead to a low pace of development and a vicious cycle of impoverished living, which will be the result for most communities within Bo.

It was also evident that several incidences of clique violence occurred in the study area, including fighting, killing, and robbery. Electioneering processes in the city mark the high tides for most of these challenges,

suggesting that political leaders who seek conflict at the expense of the masses for their gain often easily influence cliques.

Conclusion

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that several incidents of clique violence took place in Bo city. These violent activities often lead to the violation of the human rights of the residents in the affected parts of the city. Therefore, because of the threats this violence poses to the stability and peace of the city, it is convenient to state that, to a considerable extent, it affects the socioeconomic well-being of the people in this part of the country. That notwithstanding, if these cliques and their associated problems are not checked, we will lose a more significant part of our young generation to violence, which can lead to a shortage of efficient and effective human resource capital in Bo.

Recommendations

In a bid to weed out cliques and gangs that have been terrorizing citizens in Bo, the public should be able to provide helpful information that would lead to their arrest.

Civic education in schools should be adopted to mitigate the rise of cliques and gangs, and religious leaders should also help educate the public.

The police should continue to train and sensitize critical actors and community members to detect and address early signs of crime.

There is a need to enhance the existing communication system between the police and the community.

The government should be able to provide scholarships for school-going youths and provide effective free education so that people experiencing poverty can send their children to school.

Everyone should applaud the role played by NGOs, CBOs, and religious and cultural institutions in crime protection.

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